

PRIORITY TASKS OF PEDAGOGY IN YOUTH EDUCATION

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Annotation: The article discusses the inextricability of traditions and values along with a new pedagogical approach in the education of young people.

Key words: Pedagogue, youth, education, family, new methods, experience, skills.

The process of education and upbringing consists in preparing the growing young generation for life based on the social order that reflects the demands of society. In the process of education and upbringing, the personality of the pedagogue and his professional skills are of great importance in the formation of the potential and outlook of young people to acquire the knowledge, manners, customs, culture and work skills collected by their ancestors, to take their rightful place in society based on life experience. At the same time, it is a priority task of the field of pedagogical activity to form young people the qualities necessary to solve new issues and problems arising from the demands of the times. For this, first of all, the pedagogue should have the skills to impart new knowledge, to be able to engage in creative activities in accordance with the changing work and life conditions. In this regard, the President of our republic, I.A. Karimov, said, "We are facing an urgent issue that cannot be underestimated, such as providing educators with modern knowledge, improving their education and qualifications. In my opinion, this is the main problem in changing the educational system. We demand that the teacher give modern knowledge to our students. But in order to give modern knowledge, first of all, the trainer himself should have such knowledge"¹. The person is an important component of the national model of personnel training, the main subject and object of the personnel training system,

education 1 Karimov I.A. A perfect generation is the foundation of Uzbekistan's development. - Tashkent, 1997, 7 - p. 2 is defined as a consumer of services and their implementer. This created the necessary foundations for the introduction of individual-oriented education in our republic. The set of professional requirements for the teacher is defined as the level of readiness for pedagogical activities. On the one hand, psychological, psychophysiological and physical training can be distinguished in its composition, and on the other hand, scientific-theoretical and practical abilities as the basis of professional skills. Currently, we can divide the professional requirements of a teacher into three main groups: universal characteristics, characteristics that determine the special aspects of the teacher's profession, special knowledge and skills in the subject. Psychologists refer to a group of pedagogical abilities that reflect the synthesis of the mind, emotions and will of a person in the justification of professional activity. Pedagogical skills include didactic, planning, perspective-taking, quick results, communicative and organizational skills. It also includes universal human characteristics, spiritual-psychological, social-psychological, individual-psychological abilities, practical knowledge and skills, that is, general pedagogical (informational, developmental), general labor (design, organization), independent organizing (systematization and generalization of knowledge) characteristics in the psychology of a teacher. should stand out. A teacher is not only a profession whose purpose is to impart knowledge, but also a person who fulfills an important and responsible task in forming a person as a person. At the same time, the goal of pedagogical education can be manifested as a process of development of a new type of teacher's personality, which expresses the following: 3 - patriotic responsibility and social activity; - love for children, the desire and ability to give them one's heart; - true intelligence, spiritual culture, desire and ability to work with others; - high level of professional skills, scientific-pedagogical thinking in a new style, acceptance of creative conclusions and readiness for new ideas; - the need and willingness to constantly work on oneself; - physical and mental health, professional knowledge

confidence; - strive to develop levels of professional competence; - growth of desire to form individual qualities and characteristics, etc. The orientation of the teacher's personality plays an important role in organizing the teacher's professional activity. In this regard, it is possible to consider the characteristics that represent the socio-ethical, professional-pedagogical and scientific orientation of the teacher. Vocational-pedagogical orientation of professional students placed on the person of the teacher occupies a special place. It embodies the main professional characteristics of a teacher. The professional directions of a teacher include interest in the teaching profession, pedagogical talent, professional pedagogical passion. Interest in the teaching profession is considered the basis of pedagogical orientation, it is reflected in a positive attitude towards pedagogical activities, children, parents, and the desire to acquire pedagogical knowledge. finds Pedagogical talent, in contrast to pedagogical interest, refers to the passion that is formed from the ability to do pedagogical work. Whether the talent is present or not can be determined by engaging the future teacher in educational or real professional activities. Aptitude for the chosen activity is an important factor in the development process of the individual, which instills confidence in the individual's suitability for teaching. Thus, the future teacher's professional skills are formed as a result of the accumulation of theoretical and practical pedagogical experience. It can be concluded that the shortcomings during special training make the future teacher incapable of professional activity. acceptance of creative conclusions and readiness for new ideas; - the need and willingness to constantly work on oneself; - physical and mental health, professional knowledge confidence; - strive to develop levels of professional competence; - growth of desire to form individual qualities and characteristics, etc. The orientation of the teacher's personality plays an important role in organizing the teacher's professional activity. In this regard, it is possible to consider the characteristics that represent the socio-ethical, professional-pedagogical and scientific orientation of the teacher. Vocational-pedagogical orientation of professional students placed on the person of the teacher

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